

Let's grow together: Co-creating a sustainable community together with the user panel

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Abstract

Citizen engagement can be facilitated by maintaining a sustainable user community or user panel. User involvement can go further in the direction of a collaborative community model, where citizens are empowered to participate in decision-making processes and help shape the long-term strategy of the living lab. This paper presents the efforts of a living lab that is redefining its panel management to foster long-term, sustainable, and meaningful citizen engagement. Through three co-creation sessions, the user journey was explored, motivators and barriers for participation were identified, and a future community structure was co-designed. Findings reveal that personal connection, accessible communication, and meaningful involvement opportunities are critical to sustainable engagement. Participants designed new engagement strategies and proposed creating an advisory group, hybrid participation formats, and a structured newcomer onboarding system. As a next step, findings will be validated through a broader panel survey and ongoing community work. This research underscores the value of collaborative participation pathways in living labs, where panel member input and team leadership can work together to foster sustainable, impactful engagement. By transforming its panel management into a collaborative community model, the living lab can strengthen its role in the innovation ecosystem and become more resilient.

Keywords

Panel management, Sustainable engagement, Participatory design, Community management, Co-creation, Living Lab.

Introduction

Living labs are dynamic structures that drive innovation through participatory methods, bridging research, policy, and society. In these real-life environments, citizens are actively engaged in shaping, testing, and evaluating new solutions (Schuurman et al., 2016). Citizen engagement presents both opportunities and challenges, especially when aiming for long-term, sustainable involvement beyond individual projects. One way to facilitate access to your stakeholder group is to build a sustainable user community or user panel who are willing to contribute to user research within a certain context or on a certain topic (De Witte et al., 2024).

However, the role of users can go beyond participating in activities. Arnstein's ladder of citizen participation (1969) states that citizen panels can support the development of sustainable communities. This ambition aligns with the vision of the World Health Organization (2020) that participatory governance is crucial for legitimacy, equity, and effectiveness in health innovation. According to the WHO, co-design with citizens fosters inclusive systems and shared ownership. De Weger et al. (2020) further highlight the need to address power imbalances, build trust, clarify roles, and invest in long-term collaboration to achieve meaningful, lasting engagement. These factors ensure that citizen involvement is genuinely influential rather than merely symbolic.

Based on over a decade of experience managing a large citizen panel a living lab is now taking the next step toward a more collaborative community model as Lemey et al., 2015 point out. However, there still is a scarcity of research on Living Labs that critically evaluate the functioning of their user panels, moreover on a long-term basis. This paper describes the living lab's activities to codesign such model that support citizens' ongoing involvement, not only as participants in research activities but as strategic partners in the long-term functioning and strategy of the living lab.

The central research question is "In what way can we foster meaningful and enduring participation from our panel in the daily workings and broader goals of our Living Lab?" This main question is further developed through the following sub-questions:

- What would an ideal citizen journey for panel members look like, from first contact or interest to becoming a fully engaged panel member?
- Which incentives can foster long-term commitment?
- How can we co-create the development of the panel as well as identify and reduce entry barriers?

- How can we enhance and sustain opportunities for citizen participation and influence in living lab operations?

Methods

The following flow chart outlines the study's process, including the involvement of the panel and key methodological steps.

Figure 1. Outline of the study's process, including the involvement of the panel and the key methodological steps

Participant recruitment and characteristics

Participants were recruited from a living lab panel. Inclusion criteria were (1) panel memberships for more than six years, and (2) frequent participation in activities (at least three activities per year). Eligible participants received a personal invitation. All participants provided informed consent, and the study was approved by the Social-Medical Ethical Committee (SMEC, ref. G-2025 02 2238).

Co-creation sessions

The research process was divided into three thematic sessions, each building on the insights of the previous one. Each co-creation session was designed to encourage active participation and reflection through a combination of structured dialogue, customer journey mapping, and creative ideation exercises.

Session 1 – Mapping the user journey

Participants were introduced to the customer journey concept. They mapped key touchpoints in their panel experience, discussed strengths and challenges, and reflected on how interactions shaped their perceptions of the living lab. This exercise provided a foundation for understanding the user experience from a panel member perspective.

Session 2 – Motivators and barriers to participation

Using three personas representing potential panel members, participants explored drivers and barriers to participation. The session also included an exploration of appropriate terminology for describing panel members—ranging from “volunteer” and “citizen” to more creative or empowering terms like “innovation tester” or “co-creator.”

Session 3 – Co-designing participation pathways

Participants reviewed real-life engagement models (e.g., citizen panels, ambassador roles, advisory boards). These examples informed a brainstorming session on participation pathways and decision-making involvement.

After this ideation phase, participants worked together to refine ideas from all three sessions. The group co-created a draft action plan with priorities in communication, motivation, and participation.

Data collection and analysis

Discussions were guided by structured templates, with real-time notetaking by a facilitator. Input was analysed thematically by two researchers to identify patterns and key themes. Illustrative quotes were highlighted to contextualize findings. Visual summaries of each session were created in Miro and shared for feedback, ensuring accurate representation of participant perspectives. This iterative approach ensured that the findings were continuously refined and aligned with participants' evolving ideas and input.

Next steps

The study will continue with broader validation through a panel-wide survey, which include following themes: communication, interest in specific topics, and motivation. In parallel, actions from the sessions will be tested, evaluated and refined based on continuous feedback and input from the panel. After conclusion of this study, continue monitoring and assessment of the adapted procedures will be followed up to ensure their lasting impact.

Results

Demographics

Table 1 describes the sample of participants in the three co-creation sessions.

Table 1. Sample description

Session	Participants (n)	Gender (F/M)	Age categories (<60 / 60-74/ 75+)
1 - The user journey	9	5/4	1/6/2
2 – Motivators and barriers for participation	10	5/5	0/7/3
3 – Co-designing a future community structure	7	4/3	0/5/2

Strengths in current practice

Participants valued several panel management and participatory methods good practices. They emphasized the personal contact during initial onboarding, the professional and welcoming organization of sessions, and the accessible, friendly presence of the panel managers. These factors can foster trust, participant satisfaction and sense of value:

“Our input is truly listened to. I’ll definitely come back!”

“What this lab does—getting citizens involved in new developments—is good for the whole community.”

Engagement was frequently described as enriching, personally fulfilling, and socially rewarding:

“We’ve had many great experiences and have learned a lot.”

“I really enjoy coming here. I meet many like-minded people who want to think along.”

“We are not only growing together but also flourishing together.”

“I Contribute to society and improve my own insights. That’s why I come.”

“I’m amazed every time. That’s what I want—to keep feeling that sense of wonder.”

Challenges and opportunities for improvement

A recurring concern was the limited clarity regarding the living lab's mission, ongoing activities, and the roles of individual team members. Some participants were uncertain about how their input was used or whether it had a meaningful impact:

“What happened with our input? Did it help you? Did it make a difference?”

Furthermore, participants emphasized the need for clear, jargon-free language and preferred the use of native language terms over English expressions in the living lab's communication. They felt that the written communication didn't match the clarity and accessibility of the in-person sessions:

“There's a gap between the written communication and what actually happens during the sessions. The sessions are always very clear and easy to follow, unlike the written communication where a lot of complex words are used.”

In addition, participants suggested creating a simple, accessible flyer to introduce the living lab and its activities to potential new members:

“We need something easy to hand out—a flyer that explains what the living lab does and how people can get involved.”

Furthermore, participants highlighted challenges with the onboarding process of new panel members. While they appreciate the warm welcome, some felt that the intake questionnaire could feel overwhelming if not introduced properly:

“You have to make sure people really know you before asking such detailed questions. That can be a barrier for new members.”

Motivators and barriers for sustainable engagement

Social connection was the most frequently cited motivator, with many valuing the sense of community and the opportunity to meet others:

“I feel like I'm part of something.”

Personal development, the chance to learn about innovation and gain new experiences were noted as motivators along the sense of impact; the feeling that their input mattered and contributed to better care solutions.

“I feel like my input makes a difference”

However, participants also noted several barriers that could hinder engagement. Time constraints, digital exclusion and lack of relevance were mentioned as barriers:

“When I can relate to the topic, I feel more involved.”

Participants emphasized the importance of personalized outreach, clear communication and relatable topics.

Co-designing participation pathways

From several citizen engagement models, participants favoured a community advisory group of six to twelve dedicated members. This group would meet twice a year and would act as a strategic partner in the long-term functioning and strategy of the living lab.

While participants appreciated the opportunity to contribute, they also expressed confidence in the living lab to manage these initiatives.

“You handle it, we trust you.”

This reflects a preference for collaborative engagement where the team takes the lead while involving citizens in meaningful, advisory roles.

Discussion

These findings illustrate the importance of creating spaces where citizens not only contribute to innovation but also experience personal growth, social connection, and a sense of collective purpose. Participants identified several challenges, such as communication, time constraints, onboarding, and digital inclusion and proposed to set up a community advisory group. Our findings align with existing literature on sustainable citizen engagement and living labs (De Weger et al., 2020; Schuurman et al., 2016). The importance of clear communication, trust, and personal motivation is reflected both in previous studies and in our participant feedback. At the same time, this research offers a new perspective by positioning citizens not just as participants, but as co-owners of the process. The co-creation of a community advisory group represents a concrete step towards a more participatory community model. This approach has seen limited implementation in living labs, presenting a valuable opportunity to explore new ground.

A key strength of this study is our critical reflection on our own panel management. By examining the living lab practices together with panel members, we built on an existing foundation of trust. The input clearly shows that meaningful engagement is not automatic, but can be strengthened through targeted actions around communication, onboarding, and structural involvement. The living lab can now also experiment with suggestions to explore whether a community advisory group can contribute to joint decision-making and can help shape the long-term strategy of the living lab.

The study is not without limitations. The small number of participants in the co-creation sessions limits the generalizability of findings. Moreover, the participants lacked diversity as they were almost all aged 60 and older. In addition, the long-term impact of the proposed advisory model has yet to be demonstrated. Future research should and will validate these findings through broader surveys and pilot implementations to assess the feasibility of the co-designed structures. Such comparative research could reveal regional or cross-cultural differences in participation and thereby enhance understanding of how co-creation strategies can be adapted to diverse sociopolitical environments.

Furthermore, the integration with larger innovation ecosystems (4-/5- helix model) is a promising avenue for further research.

Conclusion

This research provides insights into sustainable citizen engagement in living labs. The co-creation sessions revealed that while participants appreciate having a voice, they also trust the living lab team to manage key initiatives, such as the proposed community advisory group. This highlights a preference for collaborative engagement, where the team leads strategic decisions while involving panel members in advisory roles.

The findings emphasize the importance of clear communication, trust, and creating meaningful engagement opportunities. Participants highlighted effective living lab practices, such as well-organized sessions, and the friendly, personal approach of the panel managers who serve as a Single Point Of Contact (SPOC) for the panel. The proposed advisory group could support a collaborative community model by combining citizen input with team-led decision-making, contributing to long-term engagement and societal impact.

In conclusion, this research demonstrates the potential of collaborative participation pathways in living labs to create sustainable and impactful engagement.

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